

THE IMPORTANCE OF TPR TEACHING

Mamatqulov Shaxobiddin

Faculty of Foreign Philology

Philology and language teaching: English

Student of group 320

Annotation: The earlier language learning starts, the higher the level of language acquisition. The natural nature of language learning in children, their strong imitation, the large number of children compared to adults is one of the main reasons for this. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of words, but memorize them mechanically. Teaching these children, a foreign language has its own method and methods. Because it affects all areas of the harmonious development of modern pedagogy, and consists of the search for non-existent methods and the necessary. It is for this reason that the article discusses the TPR method.

Key words: Total Physical Response, methods, language learning.

TPR or Total Physical Response is a language learning method that makes use of body movements with the acquisition of the new language. The Total Physical Response method mimics how children learn their first language. There is no expectation to produce the language at first; as a result, it takes the pressure off the learner. The focus shifts from producing the language to associating the language with words and actions and cementing the relationship between the two. Total physical response is a language teaching method developed by James Asher, a professor emeritus of psychology at San José State University. It is based on the coordination of language and physical movement. In TPR, instructors give commands to students in the target language with body movements, and students respond with whole-body actions.

The method is an example of the comprehension approach to language teaching. Listening and responding (with actions) serves two purposes: It is a means of quickly recognizing meaning in the language being learned, and a means of passively learning the structure of the language itself. Grammar is not taught explicitly but can be learned from the language input. TPR is a valuable way to learn vocabulary, especially idiomatic terms, e.g., phrasal verbs.

Total Physical Response is often used alongside other methods and techniques. It is popular with beginners and with young learners, although it can be used with students of all levels and all age groups. TPR is an example of the comprehension approach to language teaching. Methods in the comprehension approach emphasize the

importance of listening to language development and do not require spoken output in the early stages of learning. In TPR, students are not forced to speak. Instead, teachers wait until students acquire enough language through listening that they start to speak spontaneously. At the beginning stages of instruction students can respond to the instructor in their native language.

Lessons in TPR are organized around grammar, and in particular around the verb. Instructors issue commands based on the verbs and vocabulary to be learned in that lesson. However, the primary focus in lessons is on meaning, which distinguishes TPR from other grammar-based methods such as grammar-translation

Grammar is not explicitly taught, but is learned by induction. Students are expected to subconsciously acquire the grammatical structure of the language through exposure to spoken language input, in addition to decoding the messages in the input to find their meaning. This approach to listening is called *codebreaking*.

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While the majority of class time is spent on listening comprehension, the ultimate goal of the method is to develop oral fluency. Asher sees developing listening comprehension skills as the most efficient way of developing spoken language skills.

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Why TPR (Total Physical Response) has so many benefits, especially for new language learners and young learners. The combination of movement with language makes for naturally effective learning. Students actively use the left and right parts of the brain. It improves students' listening skills. Students do not have to speak until they are ready, so a "safe zone" is created, which greatly reduces stress. Kinesthetic learners (those who respond best to physical activity) and visual learners (those who learn best with visual cues) benefit most from TPR. (This is another reason why it's important to know your students' personalities and learning types.) Because no one is singled out, TPR is great for introverted students. The main way to use common physical response in the classroom: The teacher performs the action, shows it and says it (for example, "I brush my teeth"). Be prepared to exaggerate, use gestures, facial expressions, and props if necessary. Students will have to repeat the action.

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